
Participation in **H**olistic **EN**vironmental/Ecological **I**nnovations

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101037328

Deliverable D6.6 **Policy Recommendation**

Version: 1.0
Submission date: 14/07/2025
Lead: CES

Technical References	
Deliverable No.	6.6
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Work Package	6
Task	6.5
Lead beneficiary	CES
Author(s)	Sinara Sandri, Lionel Cordier, Sheila Holz
Due date of deliverable	31/07/2025 (M42)

¹

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the commission services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Version	Date	Modification(s)	Autor(s)
V0.1	31/01/2025	First Draft	Sinara Sandri
V0.2	02/04/2025	Review	Sinara Sandri
V0.3	26/06/2025	Integrating contributions from Lionel Cordier (CNRS)	Sinara Sandri
V0.4	03/07/2025	Review	Sheila Holz
	09/07/2025	Integrating contributions	Sinara Sandri
V0.5	13/07/2025	Review	Giovanni Allegretti
V1.0	14/07/2025	Consolidated version for submission	Sheila Holz and Sinara Sandri

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101037328

The content of this report reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Summary

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Challenges – Strengthening Citizens’ Voice in the Green Deal: Lessons from the PHOENIX Pilots.....	7
Challenge 1 – Scope	8
PHOENIX Recommendations to Address the Scope.....	9
Challenge 2 – Complexity.....	10
Challenge 3 – Multi-level governance.....	13
PHOENIX Recommendations in Addressing Multilevel Governance	14
Challenge 4 – Constitution of the Public.....	15
PHOENIX Recommendations to Strengthen the Constitution of the Public	15
Challenge 5 – Conflict.....	17
PHOENIX Recommendations to Strengthen Conflict Responsiveness.....	17
Challenge 6 – Trust.....	18
PHOENIX Policy Recommendations to Rebuild and Sustain Trust.....	19
Removing obstacles to citizen participation	21
3. PHOENIX Reflections on Methodological Co-Design.....	22
PHOENIX Recommendations for the Co-Design Approach:	22
4. Enhancing a new culture of deliberation.....	23
5. Key recommendations for different governance levels	24
EU Level	25
National Level.....	25
Regional Level	26

Local Level.....26

Cross-Cutting Recommendations: Strengthening Democratic Innovations Across Governance Levels.....27

Executive Summary

The PHOENIX project addresses the pressing need for more democratic and inclusive approaches to governing the ecological transition in Europe. As the European Green Deal (EGD) advances ambitious goals for climate neutrality, resource efficiency, and social equity, the role of citizens in shaping and supporting these transformations is critical. Ensuring that no one is left behind requires not only innovative policies but also meaningful public engagement.

PHOENIX set out to enhance the transformative potential of Democratic Innovations (a term used here interchangeably with participatory and deliberative processes) by identifying their key limitations and testing strategies to overcome them in the context of EGD implementation. The project focused on policy areas such as energy transition, Farm to Fork, and the circular economy, working through local, regional, and national-level pilot projects and co-design processes that integrated environmental, cultural, and governance diversity.

Through its 11 pilots, located in seven countries, PHOENIX tested a flexible methodology, called Tangram, tailored to specific local contexts and actors. These experiments revealed the need to move beyond one-size-fits-all approaches and highlighted the importance of institutional resilience, multi-level coordination, and public trust-building.

This document presents the some of project's main insights into three sections:

1. Six challenges that currently limit the capacity of democratic innovations to meaningfully contribute to the Green Deal pathway.
2. Co-design reflections, offering lessons on adapting participatory methodologies to real-world realities.
3. Policy recommendations tailored to different governance levels, including the EU, national, regional, and local levels, as well as cross-cutting measures for sustainability, education, and cultural change.

Together, these recommendations aim to support policymakers, civil servants, and civil society in building robust participatory systems that are inclusive, responsive, and capable of guiding long-term ecological transformation across Europe.

1. Introduction

Europe is on a transformative path toward becoming the first climate-neutral continent, driven by a modern, resource-efficient economy that prioritises social and environmental justice. The European Union has set ambitious targets to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, while ensuring that economic growth is decoupled from resource use and that no person or community is left behind. In the medium term, the EU aims to reduce emissions by at least 55% by 2030 (compared to 1990 levels), as outlined in the EGD, an overarching strategy adopted in December 2019, now translated into a broad set of regulatory and legal measures.

The success of this ambitious transition depends not only on policy innovation but also on democratic legitimacy and public engagement. The debate around the EGD has made clear that citizens must play a central role in shaping, supporting, and implementing the transformations it requires. Effective participation is crucial for building trust, ensuring transparency, and aligning diverse interests and expectations.

In this context, the PHOENIX project was launched to explore how Democratic Innovations can be enriched to address the complex and interdependent challenges of the EGD. PHOENIX focused on policy areas such as the energy transition, Farm to Fork, and the circular economy, recognising the need for inclusive, context-sensitive, and long-term approaches to public engagement.

PHOENIX mapped and tested democratic innovations that have been successfully applied in environmental governance around the world and examined the obstacles they face in scaling impacts. The project introduced a flexible methodological framework (the Tangram approach) designed to adapt participatory processes to diverse territorial realities. Like the Chinese puzzle that inspired its name, the Tangram methodology enabled local actors to co-design various participatory models tailored to their local needs, capacities, and environmental features. A key innovation of PHOENIX was the creation of Territorial Commissions of Co-design (TCCDs), as an essential tool for favouring adequateness and resilience of each pilot project. These commissions, in each pilot territory, brought together lay citizens, organised stakeholders, public authorities and civil servants, working alongside PHOENIX partners to co-create, test, and adapt participatory methodologies for each pilot territory. This approach grounded the participatory design in the lived realities, cultures of participation, and administrative specificities of each place.

The policy recommendations presented in this document draw on multiple layers of knowledge production throughout the project. In addition to the research and mapping phase, they were refined through the piloting phase in the 11 diverse territories, where democratic innovations were adapted and tested in their specific contexts. In the first

elaboration phase, a dedicated workshop with project partners was held during the project meeting in Szeged (Hungary), focusing on the collective interpretation of pilot experiences and validation of the recommendations. To deepen the analysis and ensure relevance across governance levels, PHOENIX convened two thematic webinars with members of its Methodological and Ethical Advisory Board (MEAB), one for each of the two challenge clusters, facilitating critical reflection on the six challenges identified. Together, these collaborative processes ensured that the insights and proposals emerging from PHOENIX are grounded in both academic research and practical experimentation. In addition, TCCD members from the PHOENIX pilots also elaborated recommendations on two opportunities. First, a discussion during the project meeting held in Tartu (Estonia), in April 2024, as part of Task 4.4 (inter pilots) for which representatives of TCCDs from each pilot take part in person, to elaborate a list of recommendations to incentivise citizens to participate in public processes and engage in the transition. These ideas were discussed in a second opportunity, in an online mini-public event, which involved pilots representatives, to elaborate the final version of recommendations, as part of Task 4.3 (Mini-public).

This policy document draws on the key lessons learned throughout PHOENIX's implementation. It is structured around three main sections:

- Recommendations for addressing the six core challenges that limit the transformative potential of democratic innovations in environmental governance.
- Insights on co-design practices that enhance participation and responsiveness.
- Forward-looking proposals to strengthen the institutional sustainability and scalability of democratic innovations within and beyond the EGD framework.

Together, these recommendations aim to support policymakers, civil servants, and practitioners in building inclusive, adaptive, and resilient participatory systems that can guide Europe through the long-term transformations of the ecological transition.

2. Challenges – Strengthening Citizens' Voice in the Green Deal: Lessons from the PHOENIX Pilots

PHOENIX's conceptual framework identifies six key challenges that limit the transformative potential of Democratic Innovations (DIs) in addressing the complexity and variety of environmental issues targeted by the EGD. In this policy document, the term “democratic innovations” is used interchangeably with “participatory and deliberative processes”, which refer to structured efforts to include citizens in public decision-making beyond traditional electoral mechanisms. These challenges correspond to critical design questions

and are grouped into two overarching categories: the organisational structure of democratic innovations, and the dynamics of communication and negotiation among stakeholders, particularly how their expectations, interests, and power relations are mediated to foster cooperation and legitimacy.

All PHOENIX pilot projects addressed these challenges at different scales, focusing on both the co-design of participatory architectures and the testing of deliberative methodologies tailored to diverse territorial and political contexts. The insights gathered from these experiences are presented below, beginning with a short explanation of each challenge, followed by targeted policy recommendations grounded in the pilots' practice.

Ultimately, it is crucial to recognise that democratic innovation encompasses not only procedures and tools, but also values and cultural assumptions. Different communities and territories hold distinct worldviews about what constitutes “nature,” who speaks for it, and what it means to care for shared environments. These underlying perceptions shape how people relate to environmental governance and should inform the design of participatory processes across all levels.

Challenge 1 – Scope

Setting adequate time-frame horizons for policies related to the EGD is a major challenge for democratic innovations. Many environmental issues involve long-term goals and delayed outcomes, yet democratic processes often operate within short political or electoral cycles and annual budgetary constraints. This mismatch leads to difficulties in engaging stakeholders in debates that appear "out of focus" or too distant in time to feel relevant. Addressing this issue requires asking: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD be made adequate to policy frameworks?*** Solutions must ensure that deliberative structures can address long-term transitions while remaining institutionally anchored. This challenge falls under the broader domain of **organisational architecture of democratic innovation**.

Environmental challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource degradation are deeply complex, not only in their scientific and ecological dimensions but also in their political, institutional, and procedural implications. This complexity presents specific challenges to designing and sustaining democratic innovations that can deliver long-term, inclusive, and transformative responses.

A core issue lies in the fact that environmental problems often require long-term vision and coordinated action across generations. This temporal scale creates a mismatch with the short-termism of electoral cycles as well as with the expectations of citizens, which are often based on short-sighted frames. Citizens involved in ecological deliberations may not

see the impact of their decisions for years, or even decades, unlike more immediate participatory topics such as designing green spaces or cycle paths. Meanwhile, elected officials may struggle to prioritise long-term sustainability goals over short-term political gains. Addressing this temporal disconnection requires institutional innovations that anchor participatory processes in stable frameworks resilient to political turnovers.

Furthermore, political and institutional fragmentation in environmental governance is often spread across multiple sectors and administrative levels, from local to national and EU-wide bodies. For citizens, this implies further difficulties in understanding where decisions are made and how they might exert meaningful influence on those gatekeepers entitled to final decision-making on different topics, or those that can play a role in incentivising transformative changes.

PHOENIX Recommendations to Address the Scope

- **Institutional anchoring of participatory processes:** Democratic innovations should be embedded within stable legal, administrative, or constitutional frameworks to ensure continuity beyond electoral cycles. This provides long-term resilience, enabling citizens to stay engaged in decisions that unfold over decades.
- **Environmental and corrective indicators:** Connect short-term participatory topics (e.g. local green infrastructure or urban gardens) to broader EGD transition goals. These indicators should be used to track progress and evaluate impact across time.
- **Time-sensitive design of participatory processes:** Design democratic innovations that reflect both short-term and long-term timelines, e.g., by combining immediate, actionable proposals with deliberations on future-oriented strategies (such as carbon neutrality by 2050 or biodiversity targets).
- **Intergenerational participation mechanisms:** Create institutional spaces that include youth, older generations, and future-focused perspectives in participatory processes. Intergenerational dialogue helps anchor long-term thinking in present-day decision-making.
- **Partisan and institutional agreements for continuity:** Promote formal agreements between political parties and administrative bodies to ensure that electoral changes do not overturn the results of participatory processes. Such pacts should protect democratic innovations and their results as shared public assets.
- **Feedback loops and progress tracking:** Regularly report back to citizens on the implementation of outcomes of participatory processes, including how they are being integrated into policies and planning at various levels. Feedback builds accountability and sustains engagement over time, especially of those individuals and groups who are more distant from (and sceptical about) traditional forms of decision-making. It is also fundamental when an institution is not directly responsible for action and decision-making in fields where citizens' proposals emerge, but accepts the role of mediator with other institutions.
- **Temporal pluralisation in participation design:** Foster participatory ecosystems that combine immediate results with long-range visioning. This can require

coordinating different channels/devices of participation that span over different and complementary temporalities (such as participatory budgets, with an annual frequency and outputs, and integrated plans referring to long-term transformations or other forms of staggered deliberation cycles, periodic citizen panels, and scenario-building exercises for future environmental policies.

- **Creation of new actors/stakeholders to address joint-action:** especially in contexts marked by significant fragmentation of governmental decision-making and regulatory frameworks (as in cross-border situations inside federal States or in regions under the control of different countries), a solution to strengthen the local communities in their capacity of dialogue and negotiation with decision-makers is that of federating civic-actors, market stakeholders and lower tiers of administrative institutions into new type of legal/formalized actors and networks with clear missions and participatory modalities of functioning.

Challenge 2 – Complexity

Environmental issues are inherently complex, spanning interconnected scientific, technical, and social domains. This complexity can discourage the active engagement of lay citizens, who may feel excluded from highly technical debates. As a result, there is a tendency to default on expert-led solutions, limiting broader democratic participation. The core problem is: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD be made accessible to all citizens?*** To overcome this, democratic innovations must invest in communication tools, translation mechanisms, and formats that make complexity manageable, accessible and attractive to all. This challenge, too, belongs to the domain of the **organisational architecture of democratic innovations**.

Complexity in participatory and deliberative processes referred to the EGD pathway is related to the fact that environmental issues involve multiple disciplines, such as ecology, chemistry, climatology, sociology, and economics, making it difficult for laypeople to understand the multiple connections and overlaps. Especially in those processes that strive to guarantee a high level of deliberative quality on the topics they deal with, the existence of a massive amount of technical information, and the need for a certain level of understanding to comprehend themes are also issues. This challenge is further amplified by the spread of misinformation and disinformation around environmental issues, which can distort public understanding, polarise debates, and undermine trust in both science and democratic processes. As a result, citizens may struggle to navigate competing narratives and make informed contributions to discussions.

Effective participation requires acknowledging that environmental challenges involve interacting systems and interdependent relationships between people, ecosystems, and institutions. Participatory and deliberative processes should therefore be grounded in a complexity-informed approach that reflects the interconnected nature of ecological, social,

and political systems, such as those embedded in the EGD. These processes must also move beyond anthropocentric and speciesism assumptions by recognising the interdependence between human and non-human life. This perspective should guide the design of participatory tools and democratic innovations, particularly in debates on energy transitions and climate adaptation.

To address complexity, it is essential to recalibrate the relationship between expert and citizen knowledge. Public engagement should not be constrained by the assumption that only experts can understand technical issues. On the contrary, citizens can contribute meaningfully to debates that extend beyond their immediate experiences, interrelating issues related to ecology with fields like the transformation of landscapes and economic activities. This requires participatory formats that promote mutual learning and value diverse perspectives, while anchoring topics that can be felt as “abstractions” by lay citizens to concrete changes related to their means of livelihood and to the quality of their daily life and socio-spatial relations. However, it is essential to acknowledge that conflicting expert opinions are a regular part of scientific discourse and should be made visible within participatory processes. Doing so enhances transparency, prevents forms of apparent consensus, and enables citizens to engage critically with different viewpoints. At the same time, scientific consensus, especially on issues such as the existence, causes and main threats of climate change, must be communicated to provide a reliable foundation for public deliberation.

Participation should be inclusive and open, enhancing cognitive diversity and legitimacy in decision-making. However, this also requires supportive action in the fields of education and media to strengthen environmental literacy and counter disinformation. Without this foundation, meaningful participation remains limited.

Finally, it is worth underlining that focusing too narrowly on the economic and financial dimensions of the EGD risks weakening public engagement. Citizens may disengage when policies are perceived as driven primarily by growth-oriented logics – and for this reason is very important to paint a picture of the European Green Deal pivoted on the ecological dimensions rather than presenting it (as frequently occurs) as mainly “a growth strategy”, although attentive to its sustainability and its impacts on the environment. Hence, to foster transformative change and collective intelligence, environmental policies must be decoupled from traditional economic growth models. Thus, democratic innovations should include mechanisms to revise and adapt the EGD in line with social-ecological priorities and civic input.

PHOENIX Recommendations for Addressing Complexity

- **Institutional anchoring:** Members of the participatory process should serve as an advisory body to the public authority designing a participatory or deliberative process on environmental topics, with clearly defined channels for communicating their inputs into formal decision-making processes, producing visible memories and outputs which are embedded in the political/administrative milieu.
- **Transparency and documentation:** All documents and materials generated throughout the participatory process must be systematically shared with participants, considering their accessibility and understandability. This ensures transparency, supports informed dialogue, guarantees institutional and civic forms of “memory” which represent a public asset and a due recognition of citizens' commitment, and – thus – contribute to reinforce trust in the process together with its perceived legitimacy and authoritativeness.
- **Expert input and knowledge mediation:** External experts should be invited to provide concise, balanced overviews of key thematic areas, highlighting areas of uncertainty or disagreement. Their role should be to inform, not dominate, deliberations, enabling participants to engage critically with expert knowledge.
- **Support for technical accessibility:** Public authorities should allocate specific funds or subsidies to enhance the accessibility of technical content. This could include hiring facilitators, translators of scientific language, or developing simplified materials tailored to different levels of expertise.
- **Knowledge support:** Staff of the public administration should be available to provide contextualised explanations of policies, data, and administrative procedures. Their role is essential in bridging institutional knowledge with civic perspectives, and requires training and incentives to maximise its effectiveness
- **Listening first:** with several actors which (also thanks to their daily work) have specific expertise in different domains related to ecology transformations, but are often marginal in decision-making dynamics, an important strategy to start an effective dialogue is that of “listening first” their concerns and interpretations of transformative phenomena that they observe daily, before organizing spaces centered on traditional contribution of external experts coming from academy or research centres.
- **Opening space to “counter-expertise”:** providing some funding for hiring “counter-experts” whose names are appreciated/pointed out by a significant portion of the participants in the process can be an effective strategy that some democratic innovations put in place to increase their perceived legitimacy and the general trust in their capacity of negotiating and mediating among differences.
- **Peer-to-peer exchange:** Structured opportunities should be created for participants to interact with technical experts or citizen panels from similar regions, enabling mutual learning and the sharing of good practices, focusing on concrete, adaptable and replicable solutions
- **Visual communication tools:** The use of infographics, visual summaries, and photo-based records should be standard practice. These tools improve

comprehension and retention, and support participants in navigating complex topics across multiple sessions.

- **Actively counter misinformation and disinformation:** Participatory processes should include strategies to address false or misleading information on environmental topics. This may involve expert clarification of key scientific facts, public communication efforts, and the creation of safe spaces for questioning and dialogue. Clarifying areas of scientific consensus and uncertainty helps build trust and ensures that discussions are grounded in reliable knowledge.

Challenge 3 – Multi-level governance

The governance of environmental issues often extends beyond the boundaries of individual institutions or administrative regions. However, democratic innovations frequently remain localised, making it challenging to optimise synergies among stakeholders across different levels. Weak coordination in these transcalar and interscalar spaces can hinder citizen engagement and the coherence of responses to environmental crises. Thus, a key question arises: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD be embedded in multi-level governance?*** Bridging local, regional, and European efforts is essential for effective and legitimate environmental governance. This challenge also pertains to the **organisational architecture of democratic innovations**.

The interdependence of planetary life and the global impact of climate change challenge the traditional assumption that participation is most effective at smaller, local scales. While local participation can offer context-sensitive, fairer, and often more sustainable outcomes, it is no longer sufficient on its own. To meet the complex demands of environmental governance, especially in the context of the EGD, there is a need to shift from a localist approach to one that embraces transcalar and interscalar participation. This involves integrating local processes with regional, national, and EU-level governance frameworks, articulating them with worldwide-spread actions and ensuring that information and decisions flow seamlessly across all levels.

Overcoming the narrow focus on mini-publics as isolated deliberative spaces is key. Attention must turn to how multiple participatory arenas interact and mutually coordinate their visions and outputs, how they are embedded in broader institutional architectures and policy frames, and how they relate to civil society and public administrations.

Strengthening communication and coordination between different levels of public administration is crucial for enhancing institutional learning, ensuring policy coherence, and supporting long-term strategies, such as biodiversity protection and the transition to clean energy. Participation must influence institutional culture and decision-making across sectors, rather than remaining isolated within one-off consultations.

Moreover, the legitimacy of local initiatives must be upheld, even when they do not scale up or feed directly into national-level processes. At the same time, expectations surrounding citizen impact must be managed transparently to avoid frustration, especially in multilevel governance contexts where implementation powers are distributed unevenly and have asymmetric relations with inhabitants and stakeholders.

PHOENIX Recommendations in Addressing Multilevel Governance

- **Recognition of national and cultural differences:** Participatory mechanisms must account for national, linguistic, and cultural diversity. These specificities should be explicitly acknowledged and integrated into democratic design.
- **Multi-level participatory ecosystems:** Develop participatory systems that connect local, regional, and national processes, enabling better coordination across governance scales.
- **Clarify multi-level governance pathways:** Develop accessible communication tools that map out how citizen recommendations flow through local, regional, national, and EU-level institutions, making institutional responsibilities transparent and visible, thereby supporting citizen understanding and enhancing trust in the process. This helps participants understand where and how influence is possible.
- **Clarify the impact of citizen input at each level:** Ensure transparency around how recommendations from participatory processes will be handled by institutions at different levels, especially within the EU governance structure. Clear expectations reduce frustration and build trust.
- **Transcalar application of democratic innovations:** Democratic innovations should be designed to operate across governance levels, integrating local, regional, national, and EU perspectives, particularly when addressing shared challenges like climate change or biodiversity loss.
- **Legitimise non-scalable local initiatives:** Even when citizen-led projects or ideas cannot be scaled up, their value and legitimacy at the local level must be respected and supported, trying to identify how they could benefit other places with similar characteristics and/or challenges.
- **Encourage coordination across participatory layers:** Facilitate structured coordination between participatory processes at different levels (e.g., municipal, regional, national) to improve responsiveness and avoid fragmentation in environmental governance, as well as “fatigue” and frustration of participants
- **Promote cross-level collaboration for the EGD:** Collaboration among actors at all levels of governance is essential to meet the EGD's goals, including the clean energy transition, biodiversity conservation, and climate adaptation.
- **Facilitate upstreaming of local insights:** Ensure that insights and innovations generated at the local level are systematically shared and considered in national and EU-level policy debates. Establish formal channels for “upstreaming” local knowledge into broader environmental governance, through dedicated platforms and/or coordinating actors/entities.

Challenge 4 – Constitution of the Public

Achieving the transformative goals of the EGD requires behavioural change and active participation from a wide array of societal actors. Yet many remain passive due to inertia or lack of empowerment. Encouraging behavioural change that leads citizens from observers to co-creators of change is essential. This brings forth the question: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD be fully inclusive?*** To respond, democratic innovations must create accessible entry points, empower underrepresented groups, and support participation through facilitation, education, and ongoing engagement. This challenge is situated in the domain of **communication and negotiation among actors**.

Recognising the interdependence between human societies and nature invites us to rethink the very notion of “the public.” Inclusivity should extend beyond vulnerable human populations to encompass the perspectives, rights, and needs of non-human actors (including ecosystems and animals), as well as future generations. Moving beyond anthropocentric and speciesist **assumptions in the design of democratic tools and concepts can provide a provocative and constructive lens** for discussions around the EGD.

At the same time, caution is needed. While the goal of inclusiveness is vital, it can become hollow if not matched with genuine power-sharing. Democratic innovations must extend beyond symbolic inclusion to enable meaningful participation, particularly for those who are traditionally voiceless or powerless. The challenge is not only behavioural, but profoundly political and structural. **Participation must begin in the conception phase of policy development, not just during implementation.** Otherwise, citizens may be invited to support and execute policies they had no part in shaping. True co-creation means transforming existing power relations and confronting uncomfortable questions: Can active partnerships dissolve power asymmetries? Is the goal a consensus or a negotiated compromise? Democratic innovations that are responsive to these complexities will be better equipped to drive just and lasting ecological transitions.

PHOENIX Recommendations to Strengthen the Constitution of the Public

- **Move beyond inclusion to active empowerment:** Democratic innovations should redistribute influence by giving traditionally excluded actors, such as migrants, Roma communities, youth, rural populations, and others, real power in both design and implementation phases. Inclusion without empowerment risks reproducing structural inequalities.

- **Embed co-creation in all policy phases:** Citizen engagement must start at the **conception stage**, not only during implementation. Co-designed policies gain legitimacy when citizens help define problems, not just execute solutions.
- **Frame participation as power-sharing:** Behavioural change is necessary, but not sufficient. Participation must challenge and rebalance existing power structures, enabling meaningful influence over policy content, not just its uptake.
- **Clarify the goals:** Democratic innovations must be transparent about whether they aim for consensus, compromise or a plurality of positions. Recognising differences and negotiating trade-offs should be seen as democratic strengths.
- **Represent future generations and non-human actors:** Build mechanisms, legal, symbolic and or participatory, that give standing to future generations, ecosystems, and non-human life in decision-making processes.
- **Legitimise environmental and social activism:** Recognise that democratic expression takes many forms and repertoires of struggle, including radical protest and mobilisation. Participation should validate the role of activists in shaping the transition.
- **Use cultural and artistic practices to widen access:** Harness creative tools and formats (e.g. from the New European Bauhaus) to include those who may not engage in traditional deliberative formats, while supporting broader cultural shifts toward sustainability.
- **Ensure participation yields tangible benefits:** Link participatory efforts to concrete improvements in living conditions, public services, or environmental quality, especially for the most disadvantaged communities and those more exposed to environmental risks.
- **Account for ‘silent voices’ and structural exclusion:** Design participatory and deliberative processes that actively seek out and compensate for structural silencing, whether through proactive outreach, facilitation, or dedicated support mechanisms.
- **Valuing the importance of social intermediation in increasing inclusiveness:** despite there is today a tendency to shape participatory and deliberative spaces where participants count and are valued for their contributions given as individuals, it is worth to recognise the important role that organised bodies of social fabric have in advocating for widespread interests and mobilising marginal and vulnerated groups to take part directly to the participatory devices and seeing their knowledge, skills and ideas recognized. Organisations involved in social intermediation are important to coagulate common narratives, views and proposals, avoiding the excess of fragmentation, competition and individualised thinking, and acting as watchdogs in monitoring institutional behaviours and performance, but also granting that society values approaches based on commoning and solidarity.

Challenge 5 – Conflict

Environmental decisions often provoke conflicting expectations and visions, particularly across different territories. Without robust deliberative frameworks, these conflicts can multiply and fragment democratic processes, pitting citizens against each other. Addressing this fragmentation requires strengthening the capacity of democratic innovations to hold plural perspectives. The central question is: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD be responsive to all?*** Democratic processes must be designed to manage and mediate conflict, enabling dialogue without collapsing into polarisation. This challenge lies within the domain of **communication and negotiation among actors** aimed at improving cooperation.

The social and territorial impacts of the green transitions, such as uneven distribution of costs and benefits, cultural tensions, and competing development models, make democratic innovations especially vulnerable to fragmentation if they are not designed to anticipate and respond to conflict. Negotiation and conflict mediation must therefore be core features of deliberative formats, especially when addressing transition pathways that require collective commitment. Furthermore, these deliberations must go beyond the human sphere: considering ecological interdependence demands the inclusion of non-human variables when assessing impacts, proposing compensations, and developing visions for a post-carbon society.

A broader perspective is needed, one that connects global environmental imperatives to locally grounded solutions. This includes linking small-scale participatory formats (such as mini-publics or participatory budgeting) to broader public debates, ensuring that conflicting views are not siloed but are meaningfully integrated. Democratic innovations should foster not only agreement but the legitimacy of disagreement, creating space for dissenting opinions while working to depolarise narratives and enable shared ownership of the transition.

PHOENIX Recommendations to Strengthen Conflict Responsiveness

- **Integrate deliberation across scales and spheres:** Strengthen the link between small-group deliberation (e.g. mini-publics) and broader public discourse. This ensures that conflictual views are processed in both intimate and collective arenas, supporting shared understanding.
- **Design conflict-aware participation formats:** Build in mechanisms for mediation and conflict resolution from the outset of participatory processes. This includes scenario building, facilitated negotiation, and inclusive agenda setting.
- **Legitimise minority positions:** Democratic innovations should formally recognise the presence of dissenting or minority views, registering explicitly such positions in

the memory of participatory exercises so that they can maintain visibility and the possibility of being re-analysed and considered in later stages. Offering tailored support (e.g. facilitation, translation, or accessibility tools) can ensure these voices are heard, respected and debated.

- **Support appropriation by grassroots movements:** Create participatory mechanisms that can be easily accessed and mobilised by civil society and grassroots actors. This enhances democratic ownership and enables more horizontal and egalitarian engagement.
- **Utilise digital tools for inclusive dialogue:** Implement user-friendly, transparent digital platforms that facilitate broad participation and the management of complex debates. These tools should support pluralism and allow asynchronous input across geographies.
- **Address the territorial dimension of conflict:** Consider the differentiated impacts of the EGD across territories when designing participatory and deliberative strategies. Compensatory measures and impact assessments must reflect local realities.
- **Depolarise narratives while embracing plurality:** Invest in framing strategies and facilitation techniques that avoid binary oppositions. Democratic innovations should allow for conflicting visions while preventing fragmentation or disengagement.

Challenge 6 – Trust

Mistrust among participants (whether between citizens, institutions, or experts) undermines the potential for collective action and consensus in environmental governance. This erosion of trust weakens support for policy outcomes and hampers long-term collaboration. The critical question here is: ***How can democratic innovations for the EGD generate and sustain trust?*** Building mutual trust requires transparent processes, accountable decision-making, and consistent feedback mechanisms. It also demands respect for diverse forms of knowledge and experience. As with Challenges 4 and 5, this falls under the domain of **communication and negotiation among actors**.

Trust is not simply a matter of transparency or effective communication; it is profoundly tied to power dynamics, procedural/throughput legitimacy, and long-term institutional commitment. The credibility of democratic innovations is threatened when participatory processes fail to influence real decisions, are unclear in purpose, or are used merely to validate pre-existing agendas. This kind of “participatory authoritarianism”, where participation is ritual and simulated rather than substantive, can deepen cynicism and alienation among citizens. Strengthening trust, therefore, requires more than individual process design: it requires transforming how institutions relate to citizens and how political mandates integrate participatory input into policies and planning.

In the context of the EGD, trust must be sustained across long timelines and diverse sectors, including legal, administrative, socio-cultural, economic, and environmental ones. The path toward a post-carbon society depends on public cooperation, which in turn relies on visible, consistent responsiveness from public institutions. Trust grows when actors understand not only the goals of participation but also how their input will be utilised, what its limitations are, and what mechanisms exist to follow up on recommendations during implementation and monitoring phases. Political parties and institutional actors play a crucial role in integrating these mechanisms into the broader fabric of democratic life.

Accountable procedures are critical where deliberative mechanisms “by invitation” (i.e. mini-publics, assemblies and panels with a reduced number of actors involved) are used. There is a risk that such mechanisms do not contribute to increasing mutual trust between larger populations and institutions, as their capacity of “representing” larger audiences is denied even when their capacity of producing meaningful and high-quality output for policy transformation is recognised. Hence, how participants are selected, the possibility of making their work known and validated by all other actors in different stages, and their capacity of incorporating and considering external inputs during the workflow of their participatory exercise are significant to increase their impact and make their perceived legitimacy and authoritativeness more robust.

PHOENIX Policy Recommendations to Rebuild and Sustain Trust

- **Clarify objectives from the start:** Participatory processes should begin with a clear and transparent articulation of their goals, scope, and limitations. This ensures that expectations are aligned and avoids disillusionment at later stages.
- **Institutionalise feedback loops:** Establish mechanisms for regular public reporting on how citizen input is used in policymaking. Feedback should not be episodic but built into the design of democratic innovations as an ongoing accountability structure.
- **Strengthen political commitment to Democratic Innovations:** Encourage institutional actors, including political parties and public administrations, to integrate democratic innovations into their internal processes. This helps normalise participation as a governance tool rather than a one-off experiment.
- **Link participation to impact communication:** Communicate clearly and regularly on how democratic innovations contribute to the implementation of the EGD. Visibility of impact reinforces legitimacy and builds confidence in the system.
- **Anchor trust in governance, not just design:** Trust is a function of governance culture. Strengthening institutional capacity to integrate, respond to, and adapt based on citizen input is as important as improving participatory formats.

- **Build shared understanding of constraints:** Clearly explain and justify in detail the legal, financial, or political constraints that may limit the adoption of citizen recommendations, to avoid the perception that participation outputs are cherry-picked by gatekeepers operating through vested interests and hidden agendas. Transparency about these limits builds credibility and supports mutual respect.
- **Ensure democratic credibility through inclusive and accountable frameworks:** The EU should support the development of participatory mechanisms at both national and continental levels, ensuring they are open to citizen-led initiatives and subject to independent, long-term evaluation to build sustained trust and legitimacy.
- **Structuring spaces for favouring interconnection among actions occurring at different levels:** the EU should shape platforms where a multilevel interconnection is promoted among participatory and deliberative exercises that operate with clear principles, here underlined in the light of the promotion of trust-building. Making such experiences visible, recognised, and networked will also value the role of institutions that commit to mediating and bridging their citizens and other institutional/administrative levels, when solutions imagined cannot be limited to the proximity level and require support of higher tiers to maximise their impacts through a subsidiarity-oriented approach.

Removing obstacles to citizen participation

The diversity of environmental, political and cultural contexts in Europe can create situations of vulnerability or specific difficulties that prevent citizens from fully participating. In this sense, local authorities and policymakers must pay attention to these issues:

- **Safe spaces for participation:** This is an important point about protecting participants, offering anonymisation mechanisms when necessary and providing a safe space for criticism.
- **Multilingualism and language inclusion:** To prevent EU linguistic diversity from hindering cooperation projects, it is necessary to facilitate the production of document versions and promote initiatives that consider regional linguistic diversity as well as the use of inclusive language.
- **Objective participation conditions:** Practical support to enable diverse participation is necessary, especially to guarantee the participation of groups as women, young people and the elderly. These measures could include holding events at compatible times and durations, and providing support for meals, travel, and childcare.
- **Emotional dimension of participation:** Participation also has an emotional dimension, which requires going beyond the rational dialogue among participants. Feelings, perceptions and repertoire of struggles of individual and organised groups must be recognised and discussed together as a meaningful patrimony of participants.
- **Friendly meeting environment:** The attractiveness of the spaces of encounter can be an important lever for involving people in discussions on ecological transition. Playfulness and an informal environment (which values the dimensions of mutual recognition and listening among differences) must be an important dimension of democratic innovations. Therefore, the latter must value civic arts and all spaces for playing, eating and learning together should be considered.
- **Construction of regulatory frames:** the formalization of participatory and deliberative processes can enhance their capacity of investing adequate human and financial resources in high-quality processes, producing broader impacts and being felt by citizens as a guarantee for the “certainty of enforcement” of the right to participation of each individual, in relation to his/her capacities of negotiation.

3. PHOENIX Reflections on Methodological Co-Design

PHOENIX tested new methodological approaches to strengthen citizens' engagement in climate-related topics, aiming to implement the EGD at local, regional, and national levels. This involved adapting and improving participatory and deliberative methodologies that had been successfully applied in other policy areas. A key innovation was the integration of local environmental features and the engagement of stakeholders in co-designing the participatory process itself, before starting the co-design process of policies and plans. These pilot experiments demonstrated that trust-building, transparency, and locally grounded ownership are essential conditions for meaningful engagement.

The key lesson is that co-designing processes with relevant stakeholders helps strike a balance between methodological rigour, responsiveness and impact. By rooting participation in local contexts, democratic innovations can better adapt to complex environmental challenges while remaining inclusive and action-oriented.

PHOENIX Recommendations for the Co-Design Approach:

- **Trust can be built through participation.** Even in contexts where institutional trust is low, participatory processes, especially those in which citizen input influences decisions, can help rebuild trust between communities and public authorities.
- **Environmental complexity does not preclude participation.** On the contrary, local ecological knowledge deepens understanding of human-environment interdependence and highlights the need for coordinated action across scales.
- **Participation must be rooted in real interests.** Motivation often stems from collective, intergenerational, and even interspecies concerns, especially when people experience the tangible impacts of environmental degradation or disasters.
- **Co-design strengthens ownership and relevance.** Participatory processes are more effective when all stakeholders are involved from the start in shaping their structure, agenda, and goals.
- **Environmental crises are windows of opportunity.** Extreme weather events or ecological emergencies can serve as entry points for involving citizens in decisions about recovery and long-term resilience planning, while contributing to recreate social cohesion of affected communities.
- **Open governance fosters trust and accountability.** Participation should be embedded in broader institutional practices of transparency, including open data, open agendas, and precise accountability mechanisms—especially for the ecological transition.

- **Environmental organisations are key contributors.** These actors often bring system-level perspectives and a mid/long-term accumulation of scientific and practical knowledge that enrich debate, without representing narrow interests.
- **Processes should be flexible and responsive.** Rigid, top-down formats limit engagement. Democratic innovations must be adaptable, inclusive, and responsive to the needs and local conditions of participants, while maintaining respect for core missions and shared unnegotiable values.
- **Micro-level agreement can support long-term sustainability.** While high-level institutionalisation is important, durable participatory culture also depends on fostering meaningful consensus at the community level.
- **Support participant learning and autonomy.** Step-by-step training in facilitation, project management, and public speaking enables citizens to build long-term capacities, create networks, and mobilise local expertise.
- **Create horizontal networks.** Former participants can empower new ones by sharing resources, methods, and experiences, thereby helping to scale and sustain democratic innovations in all phases of their development, including the implementation of recommendations and the monitoring and evaluation of their performance.
- **Use digital tools wisely.** Digital platforms are useful for inclusion and flexibility, but they are not a standalone solution. They should complement, rather than replace, deliberative formats that facilitate dialogue, reflection, and trust-building.

4. Enhancing a new culture of deliberation

Environmental issues often transcend administrative boundaries and therefore require multi-level governance, with structures and mechanisms that can effectively translate the EGD into coordinated local action. The EGD transition pathway calls for more than isolated spaces of deliberation, which requires a shared political project and collective commitment. This means carefully considering the relationship between small-scale deliberative spaces (such as mini-publics and participatory budgeting) and deliberation in the broader public sphere, with a focus on fostering inclusive dialogue that can navigate conflicting visions and expectations related to the ecological transition.

- **Building virtuous circles:** Citizen participation is significant when it generates transformative outcomes, consolidating or creating new collective rights and impacting not only policies and projects but also people's knowledge, skills, and ecological awareness. This requires bridging instrumental and epistemic dimensions of participation with the creation of new social, cultural, and relational capital. These gains should be manifested in the form of new networks, alliances, and collective fronts that bring together a diverse range of actors.

- **The necessity to confront diverse views:** In a digital world shaped by algorithm-driven "filter bubbles" that reinforce pre-existing beliefs, democratic innovations and public spaces play an essential role. They create opportunities to engage with difference and "otherness," enabling citizens to encounter a plurality of perspectives and reflect on their assumptions.
- **Including minority views:** Every idea expressed in a participatory process should be seen as a valuable contribution when accompanied by reasoning and a willingness to engage in dialogue. Minority opinions, those emerging from the margins or lacking broad support, must be respected and allowed to gain mainstream recognition. Recognising and formalising their presence in participatory settings also means providing the necessary support to enable underrepresented groups to participate meaningfully.
- **Re-thinking vulnerability:** The common understanding of "vulnerable groups" often masks structural causes of exclusion. Rather than viewing individuals or communities as inherently vulnerable, it is more accurate to understand them as "vulnerated"—that is, repeatedly harmed or disadvantaged by socioeconomic, political, or cultural dynamics. Participation must therefore be designed to challenge and counterbalance these patterns of harm.
- **Recognizing contributions issued through/by participatory exercises:** When institutions implement a suggestion resulting from citizen participation, the origin should be explicitly acknowledged in public documents and online platforms. People value seeing their input recognized and benefit from understanding the reasoning behind decisions, whether or not their proposals were adopted. This transparency fosters trust, learning, and legitimacy in democratic processes.

5. Key recommendations for different governance levels

The PHOENIX project has identified a range of governance recommendations to enhance citizen participation and democratic innovation throughout the ecological transition process. These suggestions span all levels of governance—from the European Union to local communities—and emphasise the creation of inclusive, participatory spaces and mechanisms. Key proposals include establishing permanent citizen assemblies at the EU level, promoting regular deliberative forums at regional and local levels, and fostering open governance practices that ensure transparency, accountability, and meaningful feedback. Additionally, investing in cultural awareness, equitable infrastructure, and capacity-building is essential to support sustained engagement. By strengthening connections between governance levels and adapting democratic innovations to diverse contexts, these

approaches aim to empower both citizens and institutions to advance the EGD's transformative goals collaboratively.

EU Level

- **Creating a permanent European Green Assembly for citizens at EU level**, made up of randomly selected citizens who meet at least twice a year to review and provide feedback on EGD policies. Policymakers should formally consider the Green Assembly's recommendations before laws are passed.
- **Promoting intercultural and transnational discussions on ecological transition**, explicitly involving communities and strengthening transnational networks of local actors to connect similar structures across cities and countries.
- **Formalising the existence of mixed working groups**, including citizens selected from previous pan-European participation and deliberation experiences to co-design methodological planning of future participation experiments (e.g., Citizens' panels) and to monitor the implementation and evaluation of policies and participatory processes.

National Level

- **Requiring citizen deliberations for major green infrastructure projects:** National governments should be required to hold citizen deliberation processes when planning major green infrastructure projects, allowing the public to vote or give input on critical aspects such as location, funding priorities, perceived risks, and expected impacts.
- **Investing in civic capacity and democratic innovation:** National authorities should invest in cultural and educational policies that raise awareness about the ecological transition, including initiatives such as gamified learning, training programs, thematic media (e.g. documentaries, books, festivals), and public recognition of best practices. These efforts should be complemented by support systems that help participants become autonomous actors—such as training in project management, public speaking, and the facilitation of citizen expertise networks.
- **Consolidating innovative regulatory frameworks for strengthening participatory approaches:** National authorities should discuss how to associate all interventions that can have impacts on environmental transformations with the

promotion of participatory spaces of high deliberative quality which can be required by legal procedures and also by citizens through petitions, signature collections and/or other similar mechanisms. Innovative regulatory frameworks must incentivize participation through mandatory requirement combined with calls-for-funding, prizes, promotion of communities of practices and mutual learning mechanism: they can value methodological innovation, but also need to reward continuity and evolutionary incremental improvements of participatory and deliberative exercises. Distribution of resources to democratic innovations could be proportional to their capacity of using rigorous indexes and parameters that can recognize socioenvironmental vulnerabilities of different areas and social groups, while promoting criteria inspired to socioenvironmental justice.

Regional Level

- **Making room for regional governance:** Meso-level institutions like regions can be strategic partners in multiplying local assemblies and bridging them to similar participatory tools and institutions at other administrative and political levels. This “pyramid” of interconnected spaces can serve as a foundation for wider ecological transition governance.
- **Consolidating innovative participatory approaches through incentivising policies and regulatory frameworks:** Regional authorities should combine a direct commitment in structuring participatory and deliberative spaces at the level of their responsibilities and scale with the promotion of participatory approaches to environmental matters in lower tiers of public administration. While regional authorities gifted with legislative powers can imagine to shape coherent legislative frameworks to this goal, other region (in less decentralised countries) could shape policies that incentivize innovative behaviours, included training, contributions to hire specialized and skilled collaborators, best practice awards, and the creation of platforms that can support small local institutions for conducting online and hybrid participatory exercises.

Local Level

- **Increasing regular community events:** Local citizens’ assemblies should take the form of regular community meetings where “everyday people” provide input on local green projects.

- **Establishing special offices/authorities:** To promote participation in issues related to environmental transition, public administrations could establish special coordination offices, independent authorities and participatory procedures that can activate deliberative exercises under the request of some members of elected bodies, or citizens themselves.
- **Greening public administration:** Local public entities must serve as exemplars of the ecological transition, providing clear guidelines and incentives for civil society and companies, while supporting sustainable actions with a focus on fairness and the protection of vulnerable groups.
- **Thinking globally, acting locally:** To bridge the localisation of broader policies and grassroots actions, building a network of “spaces of proximity” such as neighbourhood houses, labs, or civic centres is key to fostering community engagement and ecological transition at the local level.

Cross-Cutting Recommendations: Strengthening Democratic Innovations

Across Governance Levels

- **Ensure flexibility and responsiveness in democratic methodologies:** Participatory and deliberative processes should be adaptable across levels and contexts, allowing space for local adaptation, responsiveness to participant needs, and resilience in the face of unexpected developments.
- **Build multi-level networks to scale democratic innovation:** Create horizontal and vertical networks to share knowledge, resources, and practices across cities, regions, and countries. These networks can support replication, foster innovation, and strengthen the democratic culture around ecological transition.
- **Connect local action to broader governance frameworks:** Strengthen the link between grassroots engagement and higher-level policymaking by supporting interconnected participatory mechanisms—such as assemblies, citizen panels, and civic forums—that communicate across administrative levels.
- **Support formalisation and continuity of democratic practices:** Institutionalise participatory mechanisms through legal and policy frameworks, backed by cross-party agreements, to ensure continuity and resilience beyond electoral or political shifts.

Democratic Education

Raising awareness and fostering critical thinking about the EGD and its various measures can be significantly strengthened through diverse forms of democratic education. This includes the use of gamified learning techniques, targeted training, and accessible forms of knowledge dissemination. Cultural policies also play a key role, including the support of children's book production on environmental topics, funding documentaries, organising thematic film festivals, hosting sports events, and local fairs, as well as awards for best practices. Investing in the EGD transition, therefore, also means investing in culture and education, which are essential to cultivating informed, engaged, and environmentally conscious citizens, also valuing and enhancing the environmental sensitivity of new generations.